

Business Model Strategies to Built A Sustainable Economy for Agrotourism at Coffee Farming in Kopi Warga Study Case: Terminal

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ABSTRACT: Millennial employees had a higher turnover intention is increasing lately and it creates a bigger problem in the job industry, A recent study shows, that most Millennials are assigned to work just to fulfill pressure from their inner circle, so they chose to bury their dreams. The establishment of Terminal is offered to abridged this current problem. Most of the turnover occurs in the company affected by the millennial workforce who feel dissatisfied with their own work, or else the reversed expectation. Terminal will people with an early career stage, currently called as fresh graduates to help them find a perfect career path with the enhanced activities exploration. one of the key activities that will be tested is in Gunung Wayang, this research aims for determining the most critical and important factor impacting the acceptance of the business strategy in Agrotourism in Gunung Wayang towards terminal and execute design to be implemented for Terminal in Agrotourism in Gunung Wayang to help the agrotourism develop better in the future the research method that is used in this study is using Qualitative data analysis, through the use of an observation method such as a case study and semi-structured interview. Finally, data analysis was performed gathered data such as taped video, and audio were analyzed and coded respectively, it was used for data analysis primarily for qualitative research, and triangulation to ensure the validity and reliability of the gathered data. The correlation between the TPB and the semi structured interview that has been conducted is ruled by the positive tendencies which resulted on the both three variables the attitude towards behavior, subjective norm and the perceived behavioral control for the percentage respectively 58.3%75% and 75%. The rest of the result it is dominated by the neutral tendencies which is giving a results in the variable attitude towards behavior for 41.7%, subjective norm 12.5% and the perceived behavioral control 25% and lastly it is the negative tendencies which is resulting on the last position for one votes or 12.5% in the subjective norm variable only according to the research that has been done variables in TPB such as attitude towards behavior and perceived behavioral control give a positive tendencies towards respective subject on determining the most critical and important factor on determining business strategy creation for Terminal. In the following years, it is expected that there will be a comprehensive curriculum and structured timeline in the project execution.

KEYWORDS: Behaviour, Coffee, Gap Year, Solution, TPB

A.

B. I. INTRODUCTION

Gap years a long time started within the waves of nonconformists within the 1860s, which cruel youthful individuals travel overseas, and take an interest in volunteer exercises or paid work for a whereas. accepts that a gap year isn't restricted to traveling, volunteer exercises, or working in companies and he gives a wide definition of a hole year: people take off formal learning, preparing, or work environments to have a delay or a rest amid a period of 3-24 months. These days, the all inclusive presence of crevice a long time has ended up a noticeable include of career improvement. In a overview of approximately 2000 representatives overseas, 1/7 of members have cleared out their working environments for hole year hone, and more than 75% of them are considering doing so. In 2012, an examination conducted by Sina and EF demonstrated that 73.3% of youthful individuals needed to encounter "gap years " (Guomei & Wei, 2017)The boom within the hole year industry is most apparent within the Joined together Kingdom, were 'taking a gap year' was to begin with popularized. The gap year tourism segment has developed consistently to ended up a major frame of outbound tourism upheld by an industry of commercial and Non-Government Organization (NGO) suppliers (Simpson, 2004). In 2005 the gap year within the Joined together Kingdom was esteemed at £5bn and has been anticipated to rise to £20bn by 2010. gapa long time have also become prevalent somewhere else within the world, such as in North America, Australia, and Unused Zealand, with bounty of evidence on the Web that trade is booming. Within the U.S., for illustration, 2011 will see thirty 'gap year fair' occasions run in major cities over the nation. The gapyear advertise in Australia has as it were picked up footing in later a long

time with hole year items and programs starting to populate the websites and brochures of travel, government, and non-government organizations (Lyons et al., 2011). Interestingly, the recent global financial crisis does not seem to delay gap year tourism. In fact, gap year breaks are a much more attractive option to join the growing trend of unemployed. (Kutahlati & Viitala, 2018) As time goes on, the definition of a gap year has changed. A gap year is not limited to travel, participation in volunteer activities, but includes various other projects or activities, such as factory practice. It is considered as a kind of career break and a way to increase the academic and career chips because it can intensify resumes and is of benefit to learning and job-hunting. There are mainly two classifications of gap years practice. This result has analyzed the impact of five distinctive gapyear exercises: expanding abilities, holding up for distant better; a much better, higher, stronger and improved a higher confirmation chance, learning curiously things; recreation, work (paid or volunteer) . From a approach point of view, summarized six common gapyear exercises: work (paid or volunteer), learning, travel (organized or autonomous) and recreation. He accepts that the refinement between organized and unstructured exercises is whether it is arranged or has clear headings (Holmlund, 2008). In 2015 more than 33% of the population in Indonesia is part of the millennial generation. This number is predicted will be around 45% in 2025, more or less 170 million people. The large population of the millennial generation is an important phenomenon that must be considered (Kutahlati & Viitala, 2018) study around millennial inspiration through experimental information that collected through Facebook utilizing strategy of empathy-based stories found that millennial representatives are planning to be more spurred in the event that they are in a energetic and adaptable work. This study found that benefits, advancement openings, compensation, the work itself, work area work adaptability, and relationship with colleagues influenced organizational commitment among millennial representatives. Based on information from the Michael Page Indonesia Worker Eagerly Report, expressed that 72% of respondents in Indonesia in 2015 had an intrigued in changing employments within the another 12 months. (Alkhatiri, 2017). As a claimed to the research directed by (Karunia, 2015) that millennial employees had a higher turnover desire to quit work compared to Generation X. This made the turnover intention a problem that many companies still encountered today, uncommonly those with lots of millennials hiring. Most current reasons that millennials quit their jobs it commonly delineate as they are not suitable with the job role appointed and also a consciousness of adventure and thrill. On an enormous scale, this will affect the condition of the company. A latest study shows, that most Millennials are determined to work just to fulfill pressure from their inner circle, so in their early career stage, they often chose a job that is most likely first to get. They don't have a chance to explore what they really like and what is the most likely job they can truly be responsible for. alternative mindfulness should be paid on the gap year practice of individuals at the age of 20 and 30 years. A recent publications on the practitioners of other ages can further enrich the perception of the concept of the year at present. Peculiarly in China, more and more probing on gap year ought to anchor on the participants in other career stages, such as analysis of their motivation to turnover and participate in gap year, the benefits of gap year practice, the difference between these participants and other professionals, whether it is beneficial to their future development and the influence of gap year on the organizations that they work (Guomei & Wei, 2017). Regardless of how, a migratory spirit to explore new and different things is not a big part of Indonesian culture. Among Javanese, for instance, the idiom " *mangan ora mangan sing penting ngumpul*" (sticking together for better or for worse) leads people to get stuck in a comfort zone, surrounded by those who think, behave and talk as they do. The establishment of Terminal is offered to abridged this current problem. Most of the turnover occurs in the company affected by the millennial workforce who feel dissatisfied with their own work, or else the reversed expectation. Terminal will people with an early career stage, currently called as fresh graduates to help them find a perfect career path with the enhanced activities exploration compacted in one site "Terminal". With Terminal it is expected the users would be able to explore their abilities and hidden capabilities, through immense enhanced activities with terminal during their gap year. After the users finished the activities with Terminal, it is expected the users will be able to join the workforce with their own preferences, sense of belonging, and also responsibility.

C. II. BUSINESS ISSUE EXPLORATION

Indonesian economy has passes a prodigious systemic change from an economy where the agriculture sector plays a dominant role in the country, as preconceived in the current for roughly 45% of the total Indonesian labor workers are occupied on agriculture which reckon around 20% GDP in 2029, and it is forecasted to growing bigger in the following years. Some 30 million ha (~80.1

million acres) are under preparation by vegetation experts with about 40-50% of the cultivated land dedicated to the production of export crops. Some of around 65% of the country's cultivated land is located in Java (Indonesia Agricultural Department, 2017) Kopi Warga is one of the sustainable, recyclable and comprehensive coffee growing processes as products are transferred from plantations to packaged coffee bags. Kopi Warga is a specialty coffee brand started by a local farmer who is a member of the Agro Nusantara Farmers Group in Pangarengan. It is led by a local farmer and a community of farmers working to find the best coffee with a unique and specific character that we offer. For coffee lovers

Kopi Warga is ideal for growing coffee plants after thorough research and investigation of the inhabitants of the slopes of Mountain Wayan Windu, Mountain Malabar, Mountain Puntan and Mountain I started by deciding which area to use. Some interesting insights on soil types in the above areas, soil types, are suitable for a variety of arabica coffee or buhun coffee, formerly known as Javaprianger. From there, the observations of our team of experts continued in several coffee-growing areas, especially throughout West Java and Indonesia.

The coffee growing system is intensively carried out by local farmers who are passionate about growing world-class coffee, allowing them to produce high quality coffee that meets professional coffee standards. Start by choosing high quality seeds and planting them in the highlands suitable for coffee varieties that can grow perfectly in the Southern Priangan region. Expert coffee cultivation methods, skillful coffee cherry picking, natural drying, the best coffee bean selection process, roasting process until ready to serve coffee lovers, all of which are experienced It is closely monitored by professionals.

Figure 1. Coffee farmer at Pangalengan plantation

According to the recent interview between a researcher and the owner of Kopi Warga - , there is some idleness in the recent coffee processing activity from the plantation where only 20% of the cultivated crops were productive and the rest of them were untouched due to the lack of human resources and also the capital. The total number of hectares of Kopi Warga land is around 20 Hectares, but only around 8 hectares are fully operational; this makes an uprising problem about the unused land. Hani as the owner also said, that due of the educational skills of the farmers, the local coffee farmers in Kopi Warga plantation is also reckless while doing their jobs, Hani proposed to do a cross-plantation as mutual feedback between Kopi Warga and the local farmers, where the planted coffee plant able to do across plantation with other varieties of the other plant, such as a cross plantation between coffee and celery, that will produce a unique flavor of the coffee that is being brewed in Kopi Warga Headquarter, but due of the incompetence and lack of the education for the farmers, they were not aware that this is becoming a snowball effect for the business as a whole.

The number of the young people that is into coffee also increased in the past years, according to the study of (Sari Rahayu & Purwanegara, 2017), The current trend in Indonesia shows that with the rising standard of living and shifting to urban lifestyle, there is a change in coffee consumption patterns, especially in young people. The younger generation generally prefers to drink espresso-based beverages served at the café, while the coffee powder (ground coffee) is still the main consumption of the rural population and the elderly (Association of Indonesian Coffee Exporters and Producers). With the impact of the increasing level of public revenue and the increasing middle class, coffee has become a modern lifestyle. For modern people, drinking coffee is part of their lifestyle. Coffee tasting has become a synonym for leisure

According to (Sari Rahayu & Purwanegara, 2017) The increasing number of domestic coffee consumption is also supported by an increasing number of coffee shops in Indonesia, especially in Bandung The statement above corresponds with the current need and problem of the both of the coffee shops owner and the one who enjoys the coffee, with the participation of Terminal in this matter, it is expected able to bridge this problem, by giving the interested people the chance to experience how to handle the coffee from

the first layer of business. Terminal will be helping to create a temporary workshop that is literate and willing to do more to the impacted society.

D. III. RELATED THEORIES

In this section it will be described regarding the related theories and framework development.

E. Gap Year Concept

Traditionally, a gap year is defined as a year between schools and universities for exploring the world and career opportunities. (Piddock, 2004). This definition has been refined by (Jones, 2004) As a period of 3 to 24 months when a person takes a break from formal education, training, or workplace, resulting in a longer career path. For the purposes of this study, Gap Year refers to the period of 6 to months immediately after completing Secondary School. During this period, individuals engage in a variety of informal work, study and travel activities while considering their decisions future.

F. Motivating factors in gap-year participation

Consequently, students often consider a gap year to be a period where they can take a break from their routines and resolve the uncertainty they are experiencing regarding their future (Nieman, 2010). Students' decision to postpone higher education and start a gap year is also influenced by their financial position.

Motivations for participating in a gap year vary from person to person. The usual reasons are: 1) To broaden your horizons away from normal work and study (main reason). 2) Experience different ethnic and cultural environments to acquire survival skills. 3) enriches your resume to give you opportunities for higher education and increase your chances of getting a job. 4) Make money. 5) Contribute to society 6) Help others. 7) Religious beliefs. 8) Complete the task. 9) Looking for fun. Gap year participants want to do more than during this period to make better use of them. (Jones, 2004)

Due to their personal responsibility, young practitioners can maximize the year gap and perform better. (Snee, 2014). Volunteer motivations vary, and one of the main reasons is the altruistic tendency. They participate in gap years and better understand themselves in complex social environments (Jones, 2004). Chinese scholar and researcher (Mao Ying et al., 2015) Organized relative literature on motivations to participate in gap years using Dan's push-and-pull model (Dann, 1977), Push power comes from psychological factors and pull power comes from marketing factors. Between the pulling force and the pushing force, there are some forces related to that stimulate certain behaviors. (Mao Ying et al., 2015), as shown in Figure 2

Figure 2. Push pull diagram

G. Theory of Planned Behavior

The Planned Behavior Theory (TPB) is the further development of theory on reasoned action (TRA), taking into account the controlled behavior observed. According to this, a person carries out his intention only if he believes he can direct the action to be taken. Consistent with the sense of behavioral complexity, there are differences in the perceived controls. This view reflects one's perception of the experience and the obstacles or barriers to working. As Ajzen and a colleague of (1980) concluded, a

series of empirical studies showed the importance of perceived control in determining the link between attitude and behavior. This study supported the idea that a person with high control had a strong desire to engage in a particular behavior and would do so when considered acceptable by the researcher. According to (Vieira & Leles, 2014), the theory of planned behavior consists of consciously predicting conscious behavior, and human beings are rational analysts of the situation, and human intentions are real. It is between attitude and action. This theory was used to understand the behavior of Indonesian people or our partner to determine the important factor that is considered the best and align to Terminal business strategy and our current partner. in the below The model shown below illustrates how theory of planned behavior corresponds with each other.

After a brief explanation of the conceptual framework development above helps to see a bigger and clearer picture about how will the research will be conducted. In the table below contains a further explanation for the detailed description of the aforementioned variables on figure 10 above.

Figure 3. TPB Framework

In the variables that is used in this research is using the variables of the theory of planned behavior by Icek Ajzen in the year of 1991, the variables that were used are the attitude towards behavior, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control. This variables is used as the basis point that will framed the research well, in order to accomplish the research objectives as described before to define the most critical and important variables impacting the acceptance of the business strategy in agrotourism in Gunung Wayang towards Terminal and the expected grand design that can be carried out from this research is to help design a recommendation of the future implementation project that is feasible and mutually benefit which means both of the parties are agreed in the agrotourism of Gunung Wayang. In the table 2.1 it is described about the variables and sub variables that will played in this research process.

In order to deliver the objectives of the research project that will carried out in the point one- to determine the critical and impacting factor to the acceptance of the business strategy in Agritourism in Gunung Wayang towards Terminal , this research will be evaluating performance of the persona using observation and focus group discussion that is highlighting the key points that is corresponds on the theory of planned behavior variable, the respective value is attitude towards behavior, subjective nor and perceived behavioral control the determination of of the critical and impacting factor to the acceptance of the business strategy in Agritourism in Gunung Wayang

Figure 4. Framework development

This is the framework of the theory of planned behavior for (Ajzen, 1991) In this final project, the research leads to the determination of the critical factor that is impacting the business strategy for Terminal. According to the study by (Alias & Yusof, 2014) the success rate of a business model or project depends on whether the project meets the specific expectations of the participants. This includes owners, planners, and other relevant responsible parties, investigating the success of the project, and critical success factors (CSF) to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of project implementation. Often regarded as one of the most important ways to do it. Critical success factors (CSF) help you make decisions. With this in mind, the Critical Success Factor (CSF) was a key factor in this study, so in this study, variables are the key factors that influence business strategy.

H. Semi structured Interview and case study

In the section D regarding the semi structured interview and case study described about the questions for the desired persona and the case study of the research.

Variables	Sub- Variables	Definition	Questions
Attitude towards behavior	Attitude	Attitude is a desiposition or a prederence action to respond a matter in a certain things such as an aspira in a positive or negative way or ‘a psychological tendency that is expressed by evaluating a particular matters with some degree of favor or disfavor	
	Affective	Affective is compare ro sentiments or an feeling that's related with an state of mind question. affective reaction impacts demeanor in a countable number. The affective perspective is more uncovered into a feeling or an fondness of a individual	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. In your own opinion, what is your current aspirations, so that you choose to become man or a woman of this role? 2. How would you like to describe more about the current profession that you take a role in today? 3. What is coffee means for you?

		towards the attitude objects, the sentiments able to be related with state of mind objects in a few ways, such as classical conditioning.	
	Cognitive	Cognitive is consistent with convictions, considerations and qualities we relate with a specific question. The cognitive aspect compatible with the persons attitude determined respectively upon a consideration of the positive and negative value about the object	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is most important in taking care of coffee industry? 2. Do you agree of being a coffee specialist is as it is hard it seems as portrayed in the social media? 3. Is it hard to handle in this farming? 4. What do you think it is the important factor in creation of the coffee company or handling coffee farming? 5. What criteria would you use to asses define a good coffee company or good company farming? 6. If there is a temporary human capital what is the best criteria for you to accept it?
	Behavioral component	The behavioral component refers to past behavior wurg respect to an attitude objects	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What is your aspirations, so that you can be passionate in this field? 2. Is there any past experiences that involves to making you shaped like this? 3. How would your past experience influencing the decision making process?
Subjective norm	Social norms	Social norms are the informal, mostly unwritten rules that govern what is suitable and acceptable behavior within a certain group or society and guide human behavior. The social norms include what we do, what we think other people do, and what we think other people approve of and expect of us.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Is there any specific habitual actions in a coffee society? 2. How would the norm is shaped? 3. What do you believe it is right in doing a coffee industry? 4. What is considered good in your own terms if a person handling a business coffee? 5. In your opinion, what makes a person fit the criteria of handling a coffee industry?
	Descriptive norms	Descriptive norms are rules that describe how individuals will normally act, feel, and think in a particular scenario. These rules reflect how most people actually behave.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. If you are given a chance, about changing the coffe industry, what will be the specified action that you will likely do? 2. If there is one ideal person that would likely to help you changing the world of coffee and society what it would likely to be? Explain the criteria

Perceived behavioral control	Self-efficacy	Self efficacy refers to a person's confidence in their ability to exert control over their own behavior and over circumstances that have an impact on their lives. Self-efficacy can bring the inspiration, fulfillment, and personal accomplishment	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What do you think your most capabilities that makes you excel in this field? 2. What will be the things you will most proud of? 3. What kind of legacy you want to give further? 4. What is the kind of person or an organization you think would help the business to move further? 5. Do you think you were bron for this work? If yes then can you kindly describe it
	Perceived controllability	An individual's perception of his or her ability to exert control over internal states and behaviors as well as their external surroundings is referred to as perceived control.	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. How would you describe that your belief about this job is purposeful? 2. Is there any internal motives that makes you loves this job/ 3. Do you think is there any possibility of internal factor that will creating the people born to this job? 4. What do you think the external factors that makes you born to this job? 5. In your opinion what wil be internal and external factor of things that makes people suitable for this kind of job?

In the table below described about the case study that were given for each personal

Description	Scenario
Brief	According to calculations, approximately 45 percent of all Indonesian laborers are currently employed in agriculture, which is expected to account for around 20 percent of the country's GDP in 2029 and continue to grow over the coming years. This indicates that the agriculture sector has undergone a significant structural change in the Indonesian economy. Experts in botany estimate that there are about 30 million ha (80,1 million acres) under cultivation, with 40 to 50 percent of that area used to grow crops for export. a few of around 65% of the country's cultivated land is located in Java (Indonesia Agricultural Department, 2017)
Facts	Due to the fact that it moves the product from the plantation into a packed coffee bag, Kopi Warga is one of the comprehensive sustainable and circular coffee industry processes. The Agro Nusantara farmer group in Pangalengan, which was founded by local farmers and a community of farmers dedicated to trying to find the best coffee with distinctive and specific characters for us to serve to coffee connoisseurs, is where the idea for the specialty coffee brand Kopi Warga originated.

Problem Statement	According to the recent interview between a researcher and the owner of Kopi Warga - , there is some idleness in the recent coffee processing activity from the plantation where only 20% of the cultivated crops were productive and the rest of them were untouched due to the lack of human resources and also the capital. The total number of hectares of Kopi Warga land is around 20 Hectares, but only around 8 hectares are fully operational; this makes an uprising problem about the unused land. Hani as the owner also said, that due of the educational skills of the farmers, the local coffee farmers in Kopi Warga plantation is also reckless while doing their jobs, Hani proposed to do a cross-plantation as mutual feedback between Kopi Warga and the local farmers, where the planted coffee plant able to do across plantation with other varieties of the other plant, such as a cross plantation between coffee and celery, that will produce a unique flavor of the coffee that is being brewed in Kopi Warga Headquarter, but due of the incompetence and lack of the education for the farmers, they were not aware that this is becoming a snowball effect for the business as a whole.
Supporting Facts	The number of the young people that is into coffee also increased in the past years, according to the study by (Sari Rahayu & Purwanegara, 2017), The current trend in Indonesia shows that with the rising standard of living and shifting to an urban lifestyle, there is a change in coffee consumption patterns, especially in young people. The younger generation generally prefers to drink espresso-based beverages served at the café, while the coffee powder (ground coffee) is still the main consumption of the rural population and the elderly (Association of Indonesian Coffee Exporters and Producers). With the impact of the increasing level of public revenue and the increasing middle class, coffee has become a modern lifestyle. For modern people, drinking coffee is part of their lifestyle. Coffee tasting has become a synonym for leisure According to (Sari Rahayu & Purwanegara, 2017) The increasing domestic coffee consumption is also supported by an increasing number of coffee shops in Indonesia, especially in Bandung.
Solution Offered	The statement above corresponds with the current need and problem of both the coffee shops owner and the one who is enjoying the coffee, with the participation of Terminal in this matter, it is expected able to bridge this problem, by giving the interested people the chance to experience how to handle the coffee from the first layer of business

For the data collection method will be using Focus Group Discussion and the Case study for the selected partner. The respondent will be included as:

- 1) Coffee business expert
- 2) Kopi Warga Owner
- 3) Operational people in the coffee farming

Before doing a data collection with the selected people that will match the criteria, researchers will be doing a survey in the related area, the survey is intended so that the researchers know the natural habitat of the Interview participants, and are able to convey about the daily activities and habits of the coffee specialist. After a thorough survey, researchers will select the people from the desired criteria to be used as Interview Participants, the Interview participants will be given a case study so that they will be aware of the topics that will be displayed.

In the table below described about the profile for each respondent that will complied and agreed to do interview

Name of Respondents	Age	Current profession	Duration and the background in the industry	Motivations and aspirations
Hanifah Hasna Rahayu	26	Kopi Warga Owner	She have been involved in Kopi Warga Business from uphill to downhill since 2018, she owns kopi warga and currently her business is to manage the coffeeshop that is located in the dago bandung	She wants to help a lot of people through revolutionizing the coffee industry, this is aligned as she said in her vision to make Indonesian coffee as a good specialty coffee in the world
Yanto Prasetyo	36	Operational people in the coffee farming	Yanto have been involved with kopi warga since 2019, lately his business is to manage the operational activities of coffee farming in the dago area	Her current motivaions and aspirations is just to be driven to becoming a good human being that is committed to his work, without any calamity and corruption
Rani Mayasari	42	Coffee business expert	Rani mayasari is the owner of java halu coffee farm and as well she is a q grader coffee, she has been operating the business since 2020	Her motivations is to make a coffee beans in Indonesia have a world export standards, aside she likes to empwer people around mount halu
Tita Herlina	34	Operational people in the coffee farming	Tita herlina is the wife of Yanto prasetyo, she has been involved in the kopi warga coffee farming that is located in dago since 2019, but right now she is becoming the coffee bean sorter	Tita current asirations as per now is to support her dearest husband while maintaining the condition of dago coffee farm

IV. CONCLUSIONS

According to the data that have been obtained before there is a tendency where each people respond positively to each questions in the interview, or else they respond negatively due of the personal reasons or else people who choose neutral that is think that there is no tendency between answering positive or negative things, and just think that things it is should be run as it is. In the graphic below, it is served between the nominal or a percentage of the tendencies using graphs that representes the degree of favor people ranging from positive tendencies, negative tendencies or neutral tendencies.

A. TPB Correlation Analysis

Attitude Towards Behavior

In this section it is described regarding the degree of favor between the correlation of TPB and the results of the semi-structured interview, in the Attitude Towards Behavior there is a three variables that is influencing the attitude towards behavior, namely affective, cognitive and the behavioral component. In this variables there is three sub variables and four type of the respondent that is sever according to their job function and industry which is resulting there will be twelve answers accordingly that represents the degree of favor in the positive, negative and neutral tendencies for each respondent

Attitude Towards Behaviour

Figure 5. Percentage of the interview correlation

In the picture above described about the representation of degree of favor among the participants in the semi-structured interview that has been done in the research. According to the graphic above the number of the participants who respond positively agree towards the interview in the attitude towards behavior section is on the percentage of 58.3% or seven votes on the positive tendencies, and the rest choose neutral that represents in the percentage of 41.7% or five votes.

Subjective Norm

In this section it is described regarding the degree of favor between the correlation of TPB and the results of the semi-structured interview, in the Subjective Norm there is a two variables that is influencing the Subjective Norm, namely social norm and subjective norm In this variables there is two sub variables and four type of the respondent that is sever according to their job function and industry which is resulting there will be eight answers accordingly that represents the degree of favor in the positive, negative and neutral tendencies for each respondent.

Subjective Norm

Figure 6. Percentage of the interview correlation

In the picture above described about the representation of degree of favor among the participants in the semi-structured interview that has been done in the research. According to the graphic above the number of the participants who respond positively agree towards the interview in the subjective norm section is on the percentage of 75% or six votes on the positive tendencies, and the rest choose neutral and negative tendencies that represents in the percentage of 12.5% or 1 votes respectively.

Perceived Behavioral Control

In this section it is described regarding the degree of favor between the correlation of TPB and the results of the semi-structured interview, in the Perceived Behavioral Control there is a two variables that is influencing the Perceived Behavioral Control, namely self-efficacy and perceived controllability In this variables there is two sub variables and four type of the respondent that is sever according to their job function and industry which is resulting there will be eight answers accordingly that represents the degree of favor in the positive, negative and neutral tendencies for each respondent

Perceived Behavioural Control

Figure 7. Percentage of the interview correlation

In the picture above described about the representation of degree of favor among the participants in the semi-structured interview that has been done in the research. According to the graphic above the number of the participants who respond positively agree towards the interview in the perceived behavioral control section is on the percentage of 75% or six votes on the positive tendencies, and the rest choose neutral and negative tendencies that represents in the percentage of. 25.0% or two votes respectively.

B. Recommendation

After describing the degree of favor regarding the correlation between TPB and the semi structured interview that has been conducted, later on we are processing on determining the key factor of the important and the most critical factor towards the acceptance of the business strategy terminal in Kopi Warga Agribusiness. In this section it will be derived the most important factor according to the operational things and personal things. Operational things included the technical things that we should have prepared and the personal things is about the personality of the individual. In the table below described about the operational and personal things qualifications according to the semi structured interview that have been conducted.

Operational	Personality
1) the season of the participation should be exact 2) concern about the coffee operational things ranging from uphill and downhill 3) have a good quality services 4) good and comprehensive idea plan that is included from the exact time and date, learning objective 5) do not use any perfumery and smoke as it will be affecting the senses 6) able to do a lot with ground worker 7) know a little bit about agriculture and fertilization	1. self starter and can do attitude 2. able to do the innovation things according to the problem that they have find 3. able to be honest, cooperative and do things whole heartedly 4. need to learn something from bottom 5. have the exact purpose or goal to do

In light of the overall findings of this final research project, there are conclusion derived that could be used to address three research questions and objectives as stated below.

V. CONCLUSIONS

- 1) The correlation between the TPB and the semi structured interview that has been conducted is ruled by the positive tendencies which resulted on the both three variables the attitude towards behavior, subjective norm and the perceived behavioral control for the percentage respectively 58.3%; 75% and 75%. The rest of the result it is dominated by the neutral tendencies which is giving a results in the variable attitude towards behavior for 41.7%, subjective norm 12.5% and the perceived behavioral control 25% and lastly it is the negative tendencies which is resulting on the last position for one votes or 12.5% in the subjective norm variable only
- 2) According to the objectives of the research to find a critical and important factor determining the acceptance of the business strategy, there is two qualifications that must be agreed. The factors are the operational and the personality of the persona that is agreed to be joining. The operational and the personality qualifications are have been described in the chapter 3 in the subsection 3.3.2

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